

On a new Series of Double Sulphates of the Copper-Magnesium Group and the Sulphonium Bases. Part II.

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It has already been shown that sulphates of the copper-magnesium group yield with the alkyl sulphonium sulphates double salts which in the case of the ethyl derivative conform generally to the formula $M''SO_4 \cdot (R,S)_2SO_4 \cdot 10H_2O$ (i) where M'' = a metal of the vitriolic series and $R = Et$.

Exceptions were found in the cases of magnesium and manganese, which yielded salts of the type $2M''SO_4 \cdot (R,S)_2SO_4 \cdot 11H_2O$ (ii) (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 37).

In the present communication the action of trimethyl sulphonium sulphate upon the above vitriolic sulphates has been studied. It has been found that double salts of the first type are almost invariably formed, the only difference being that they are octa-hydrated instead of being deca-hydrated. Nickel and cobalt seem in the first instance to present certain anomalies. The first crops of these salts conform to the second type or to a mixture of the two types; but the subsequent crops are invariably of the first type.

The properties of these double sulphates are very similar to those obtained from triethyl sulphonium sulphate and the vitriolic sulphates; the only difference being in the degree of stability, deliquescent character and crystalline shape of the substances. For whilst the triethyl sulphonium double sulphates (*loc. cit.*) crystallise in needles, the corresponding trimethyl compounds crystallise in plates. The latter are much more stable and less hygroscopic than the former. The trimethyl sulphonium double sulphates are all readily soluble in water and when the concentrated aqueous solutions are treated with alcohol, hepta-hydrated double salts are precipitated. In the case of cobalt, however, the salt is hexahydrated while the nickel salt under similar circumstances remain unchanged as to the degree of hydration. In this respect these double salts show a marked contrast to the triethyl sulphonium double sulphates (*loc. cit.*). This difference of behaviour may be ascribed to the fact that while the triethyl sulphonium sulphate is extremely soluble in alcohol, the corresponding trimethyl compound is only sparingly so.

EXPERIMENTAL.

General Method of Preparation.—The component inorganic and organic sulphates respectively were mixed in the proportion of 1:2 as it was found by previous experience that if they are mixed in equimolecular proportions, at first only the vitriolic sulphates crystallise out.* The solution was concentrated at first in a vacuum over sulphuric acid and finally left to spontaneous evaporation. The crystals obtained were drained free from the mother-liquor and dried between folds of filter paper. These were then powdered and completely dried in air before analysis.

Ferrous-trimethyl-sulphonium Sulphate.—The crystalline double salt was coloured like ferrous ammonium sulphate. (Found: Fe, 10·30, 10·34; C, 13·96; H, 6·18. $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot \{(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{S}\}_2 \cdot \text{SO}_4 \cdot 8 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Fe, 10·26; C, 13·18; H, 6·23 per cent.).

On treating the concentrated aqueous solution with alcohol a white crystalline compound was precipitated. (Found: Fe, 10·65. $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot \{(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{S}\}_2 \cdot \text{SO}_4 \cdot 7 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Fe, 10·67 per cent.).

Zinc-trimethyl-sulphonium sulphate was obtained as a white crystalline substance. (Found: Zn, 11·65; SO_4 , 36·08. $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot \{(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{S}\}_2 \cdot \text{SO}_4 \cdot 8 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Zn, 11·71; SO_4 , 34·59 per cent.).

On precipitation of a concentrated solution of the salt with alcohol, a finely divided white crystalline compound was obtained. (Found: Zn, 12·14. $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot \{(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{S}\}_2 \cdot \text{SO}_4 \cdot 7 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Zn, 12·15 per cent.).

Cadmium-trimethyl-sulphonium sulphate was a white crystalline compound. (Found: Cd, 18·91; SO_4 , 32·81. $\text{CdSO}_4 \cdot \{(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{S}\}_2 \cdot \text{SO}_4 \cdot 8 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cd, 18·64; SO_4 , 31·86 per cent.).

Treatment with alcohol of a concentrated aqueous solution of this substance yielded a white crystalline precipitate. (Found: Cd, 19·10; SO_4 , 33·24. $\{(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{S}\}_2 \cdot \text{SO}_4 \cdot 7 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cd, 19·04; SO_4 , 32·82 per cent.).

Magnesium-trimethyl-sulphonium sulphate was obtained as a transparent crystalline substance. (Found: Mg, 4·76; SO_4 , 37·33; C, 12·85; H, 6·73. $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot \{(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{S}\}_2 \cdot \text{SO}_4 \cdot 8 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Mg, 4·72; SO_4 , 37·31; C, 13·98; H, 6·60 per cent.).

* It has subsequently been found that in the present case by using equimolecular proportions of the component sulphates, the double salt may also be formed.

On adding alcohol to a concentrated aqueous solution of the substance a white crystalline compound was precipitated. (Found: Mg, 4.92. $\text{MgSO}_4\{(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{S}\}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Mg, 4.89 per cent.).

Copper-trimethyl-sulphonium sulphate was obtained as a blue crystalline compound. (Found: Cu, 11.53. $\text{CuSO}_4\{(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{S}\}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 11.48 per cent.).

Addition of alcohol to a concentrated aqueous solution of the substance caused a blue crystalline compound to be precipitated. (Found: Cu, 11.87. $\text{CuSO}_4\{(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{S}\}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 11.86 per cent.).

Manganese trimethyl sulphonium Sulphate.—The double salt was coloured slightly pink. (Found: Mn, 10.27, 10.25. $\text{MnSO}_4\{(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{S}\}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Mn, 10.09 per cent.).

Precipitation with alcohol from a concentrated aqueous solution of the substance yielded a slightly pink coloured (nearly white) crystalline compound. (Found: Mn, 10.55. $\text{MnSO}_4\{(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{S}\}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Mn, 10.42 per cent.).

Nickel trimethyl sulphonium sulphate was obtained as a green-crystalline compound. In the first crop the ratio of the number of nickel atoms to the number of SO_4 radicals was 2:3 as described in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*). But the second and the subsequent crops on analysis were found to be of the usual type. (Found: Ni, 10.40, 10.58; C, 12.59; H, 6.19. $\text{NiSO}_4\{(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{S}\}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 10.69; C, 13.11; H, 6.19 per cent.).

Cobalt trimethyl sulphonium Sulphate.—This double salt was coloured like cobalt sulphate crystals. The first crop on analysis was found to be of indefinite composition as the metal did not exist in any simple ratio with the SO_4 radical and hence by analogy with the nickel compound it was evident that the substance was made up of a mixture of the two types (i) and (ii). The second crop and the successive crops were of the general type. (Found: Co, 11.19. $\text{CoSO}_4\{(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{S}\}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 10.74 per cent.).

The substance obtained from a concentrated solution of it by precipitation with alcohol was also coloured like cobalt sulphate. (Found: Co, 11.53. $\text{CoSO}_4\{(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{S}\}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 11.50 per cent.).

Water of Crystallisation of the Double Salts.—The number of water molecules has been determined by direct combustion. The number of hydrogen atoms in excess of that required by the organic component gives that present as water. Estimation of water by

simply heating cannot strictly be relied upon, since on heating even at 110° — 115° the molecules of the double salt decompose, a portion of the organic component escaping along with some molecules of water. The double salts again exhibit various degrees of stability on heating to the same temperature. It has been found that in the case of the cadmium compound on heating to 115° , nearly seven molecules of water can be driven out along with traces of the organic component. (Found, dehydrated product: Cd, 24.00; C, 14.57; H, 4.77. $\text{CdSO}_4 \cdot \{(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{S}\}_2 \cdot \text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cd, 23.40; C, 15.00; H, 4.19 per cent.).

The magnesium compound loses eight molecules of water on heating at 115° . (Found: loss in weight, 27.42. $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot \{(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{S}\}_2 \cdot \text{SO}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires 27.99 per cent. loss on complete dehydration. The dehydrated product on analysis gave C, 19.39; H, 5.63* per cent. ($\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot \{(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{S}\}_2 \cdot \text{SO}_4$ requires C, 19.40; H, 4.89 per cent.).

By heating the double salts to higher temperatures than described above, it was found that continuous loss of weight occurred, indicating decomposition, which was most conspicuous by the evolved smell of methyl sulphide.

Some of the physical properties of this series of compounds including their crystallography will form the subject of a subsequent communication.

In conclusion we avail ourselves of this opportunity to express our sincere thanks to Mr. K. C. Bose-Rây for his kind help in conducting some of the analyses.

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Received December 13, 1927.

* Owing to the intense hygroscopic character of the dehydrated salt some moisture is absorbed during operation and thus hydrogen comes out too high.

Note.—In support of the formulae assigned to the salts it may be emphasised that successive crops of the same preparation always give identical analytical results and that the resemblance between all the members of the series points to their having the same degree of hydration.